

Comparative Linguistic Statistics of Russian-Uzbek Pseudonyms

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Abstract. *Russian Russian and Uzbek pseudonyms and their place among other types of anthroponyms and in the field of Russian and Uzbek anthroponymy are considered in the article, the history of the formation of names and pseudonyms is analyzed. Classification of pseudonyms depending on the profession, methods and models of formation of pseudonyms. Russian and Uzbek pseudonyms. Literary, stage and political Russian pseudonyms of the XVIII–XXI centuries and Uzbek pseudonyms of the XV–XXI centuries.*

Key words: *ethnographic traditions, gender, metaphorical or metonymic transfer, anthroponymy.*

Aliases are the result of metaphorical or metonymic transfer of meaning. They demonstrate the native speaker's idea of the universe, how he perceives it. Pseudonyms are a product of rethinking reality, the activity of human consciousness and thinking. A person rethinks the world at the expense of accumulated knowledge, which in consciousness are grouped into categories. In this process, aliases are formed in the language. and, at the same time, both. Observance of the foundations of the existence of the Russian and Uzbek languages in the system of anthroponymy, their appearance, and certain views indicates that the nomination has always been affected. Despite the fact that it has undergone certain changes in different historical periods, has been a national tradition used since ancient times, it has not been able to completely change the basic motives. These motives are as follows: nominative, that is, the requirement to name a person; national ethnographic traditions, customs, beliefs, representations; aesthetic motives, that is, we choose a beautiful name for the child, evaluate the name by beauty; moral and educational motives, that is, to give the child a name expressing the concept of the desire to be a morally mature, perfect person in the future; religious motives, although this motive has changed due to certain historical circumstances, its main content is religious faith. This motif was one of the leading ideas when choosing a name for a child. For example, the conversion of the Turkic peoples to Islam greatly influenced their system of anthroponymy. The above motives play the role of the main factor in the emergence of Russian and Uzbek names, the formation and enrichment of the nominal fund. All the above motives are extralinguistic (non-linguistic) factors in the development of Russian and Uzbek anthroponymy, which are also studied by ethnolinguistics, sociolinguistics, the fields of history, culture. Russian women of the XVIII–XIX centuries, in order to hide their belonging to the weaker sex, were forced to engage in creative work under male names. For example, A.Ya. Panaeva under the pseudonym N. Stanitsky; Karolina Pavlova – A newly discovered poet; E.P. Lachinova – Khamar-Dabanov (novel "Tricks in the Caucasus", 1844; there is a mountain range Khamar-Daban in Eastern Siberia); sisters A.A. Lachinova – P. Letnev and P.A. Lachinova –A. Volsky; sisters-novelists Sofia Khvoshchinskaya – Ivan Vesenyev, Nadezhda Khvoshchinskaya – V. Krestovsky, they also signed themselves with the pseudonyms N. Kuratov, V. Porechnikov, N. Vozdvizhensky; E.V. Kologrivova – Fedor Fan-Dim . The works of these women were weak. V.G. Dmitriev, quoting the words of Russian critics (p. Vengerov, I. Turgenev, V. Doroshevich) about these authors, he says that none of them became the Russian George Sand. However, despite the harsh statements of I.S. Turgenev,

highly appreciating the "Ukrainian folk Stories" of Marko Vovchok (M.A. Vilinskaya; Vovchok is the name of the village near Nemirov, where she lived), translated them into Russian; V.D. Komarova, who acted under the pseudonym Vladimir Karenin for a monograph on George Sand (vol. 1, 1899) was awarded the Legion of Honor by the French government. It is noted that the motives of the pseudonymous nomination may be psychological and social factors that exist and persist to this day. Some of them are listed below:

- 1) the author's appearance;
- 2) helps a novice writer to remain unrecognized in case of failure;
- 3) the opportunity to express your thoughts freely and remain unpunished;
- 4) gender-specific, many female writers, in order to avoid sexism and gender stereotypes, chose male names or used only initials;
- 5) bilingual creativity;
- 6) creative work in different genres;
- 7) replacing an overly long name with a shorter, memorable one;
- 8) compliance with the chosen type of activity, civic position, personal creative goal;
- 9) hide your origin, in particular your nationality;
- 10) the desire to emphasize one's origin, nationality;
- 11) avoid identical surnames or names existing in the same field;
- 12) choosing a quick-to-remember, ringing name to become famous;
- 13) fear of losing your job;
- 14) to express more vividly the main feature of his nature, his creativity, the dominant notes;
- 15) the factor of re-naming (in a peripheral character) - when a pseudonym is assigned by others in order to evaluate and show the main feature of the writer's nature, his work, the dominant notes in his works, they are called tachallus nicknames or tachallus periphrases;
- 16) fear of being recognized by parents who do not want their children to be published;
- 17) emphasize your social position;
- 18) express your political views;
- 19) indicate the profession, occupation, title, social position of the author (titlonyms, from Latin. title);
- 20) the author's desire to be like his idol. Such pseudonyms are called allonyms or heteronyms (from Greek. someone else's name);
- 21) to give a comic effect;
- 22) to designate by a single name the general activity of a group of persons, and, conversely, what is written by one author is given out as the fruit of the creativity of several persons;
- 23) the discordance of his real name;
- 24) the discordance of the real name.

These 24 socio-psychological motives for the emergence of pseudo-products are divided into two groups: esoteric and advertising and aesthetic. Thus, 24 factors of adopting pseudonyms are considered, hence it becomes clear that there are more reasons for advertising and aesthetic self-presentation than esoteric motives for self-presentation. A large number of pseudonyms of Russian writers belong to the late XIX – early XX centuries. The end of the 19th century was characterized by the adoption of mostly proper pseudonyms (50%), cryptonyms (30%), payzonims (20%); Uzbek writers of this period were characterized by proper pseudonyms (50%), payzonims (40%),

cryptonyms (10%). In the second half of the 20th century, the Uzbek language developed a three-component system of proper names. Russian-international names have become popular. This process is reflected in the pseudonyms. An alias is a system that represents the name of a specific and indefinite referent. Russian creators mostly used reference names, while most Uzbek authors used a system of reference indefinite names. Pseudonyms in Russian and Uzbek express the linguistic and cognitive and psychological codes of language users as a product of linguistic consciousness embodying national cultural, mental characteristics.

Pseudonyms in Russian and Uzbek languages have the property of polyfunctionality. Pseudonyms perform extralinguistic: esoteric (ideological, national-cultural), advertising and propaganda (informative, epistemological); linguistic: identifying, nominative deictic), (differentiating, cumulative; speech: pragmatic (characteristic, expressive, aesthetic), textual functions. The epistemological function of pseudonyms is active in the Uzbek language. Nicknames and pseudonyms refer to a specific person and indicate that a person exhibits personal deixis. The lexeme of the nickname (lakab) in the modern Uzbek language has undergone a narrowing of meaning and acquired a negative connotation.

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